

EVIDENCE REVIEW: Impacts of physical activity and/or nutrition interventions in older adults

Types of interventions reviewed

Strength training

Increases muscle strength by making your muscles work against a weight, force or your own body weight.

Aerobic exercise

Also known as “cardio.” Your breathing and heart rate will increase during aerobic activities. Examples: walking, cycling

Mind-body exercise

Combines body movement, mental focus, and controlled breathing. Examples: Tai Chi, Pilates, yoga.

Supplements plus strength

Nutritional supplements (**NOT healthy eating**) combined with strength training.

Dance

The movement of the body in a rhythmic way, usually to music.

General physical activity

Any combination of aerobic, strength, mind-body and balance exercises.

Impacts of interventions

Heart health

Blood pressure, cardiovascular fitness

Daily function

Getting out of chair, walking speed, flexibility

Balance

Reaching for items, standing on one foot

Falls prevention

Injuries from falls, fear of falling

Muscle strength

Upper body, lower body and handgrip

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<https://achru.mcmaster.ca/research-studies/embolden-trial-partnering-older-adults-and-communities-develop-and-test-community>

LABARGE CENTRE FOR MOBILITY IN AGING

EMBOLDEN

Getting Out for Health

EVIDENCE REVIEW RESULTS: Type of physical activity and/or nutrition intervention and impacts on outcomes

Benefit

No change

n/a

Not measured

Heart health

Daily function

Balance

Falls prevention

Muscle strength

Strength training

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Aerobic exercise

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Strength + aerobic

Mind-body

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Supplements + strength (NOT healthy eating)

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n/a

n/a

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Dance

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General physical activity

n/a

